

A Study On Consumer Satisfaction In Distance English Language Education

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ABSTRACT: In this study, it was aimed to determine how consumers who receive distance education services evaluate this education and to determine the factors and expectations that enable individuals to turn to distance education. In this context, by determining the effects of distance education quality, perceived benefit, perceived convenience and advantage on consumer satisfaction, it is aimed to contribute to the marketing strategies that institutions will develop for distance education service. In the research, data from 403 users of an institution providing distance education in English were collected using a survey method; The data obtained was tested using the SPSS 20 package program. Research findings show that the quality characteristics (content quality, teacher quality, accessibility, and usability) of distance education positively affect the perceived benefit, perceived convenience and advantage. The perceived benefit from distance education and the perceived convenience and advantage also affect customer satisfaction positively. Accordingly, distance education service enterprises, which can improve the content quality, the quality of teachers and provide easy accessibility, also ensure the satisfaction of the buyers. In addition, it was concluded that the effects of the relevant variables on the satisfaction of users who receive distance education services differ on the basis of the demographic characteristics of the users.

KEYWORDS-Distance Education, Distance Learning Methods, Distance Learning Marketing

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is an important area that shows the level of development of societies. While the investment in this field offers a better quality of life to individuals, it also reveals the development of societies as welfare level. Rapid developments in information and communication technologies have increased the importance of distance education as well as formal education. This situation, which is important in terms of providing equality of opportunity among the individuals of the society, enables the enterprises providing education services to turn to distance education. The subject is too important to be provided only with technical infrastructure and it is as important as the subject of educational science as it is a marketing subject due to its economic value.

Educational marketing as a sub-topic of service marketing should be evaluated with a marketing strategy that businesses will create on technical infrastructure and pedagogical values. Primarily target markets must be determined by studying the market strategy and then the marketing strategy should be created and implemented for each market segment.

Research was conducted on the receivers of an institution providing distance English education within the scope of this study. The conceptual model of the research was created by considering the concepts in the

literature in the light of the studies conducted in this field. Target recipients were reached via e-mail and were asked to fill in the questionnaire form prepared and analyzed through 403 questionnaires suitable for the returned valuation. Therefore, the most important limitations of the research are that an institution covers its recipients and only distance English education is targeted.

II. DEFINITION AND SCOPE OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

The most important reason for the emergence of the distance education concept is that teachers and students cannot be present at the same time and place for a large part of the education process. Teachers and learners also need appropriate communication technologies to communicate and interact because they are in different places. Distance education practices, which were impossible for societies in the past years, have become easily applicable today with the developments in information technologies.

The Internet and digital technologies developed in parallel with it have begun to change the life and business DNA of societies, civilizations, in short, the whole world especially in the last decade. This change is so fast that a technology that we knew and used a month ago may become obsolete after a month. What is important is that these new technological opportunities are used for the benefit of society and humanity and that societies reach better living conditions by making maximum use of these developments.

It is clear that the increase in speed on the internet and developments in digital technologies have a positive contribution to the education sector and will continue to increase. Concept of distance education is rapidly entering every aspect of our lives thanks to these technologies. Since the ideal of equal opportunities in education will be reached, the increase in the level of education of individuals will also be faster when distance education systems are effective in all aspects.

Moore and Kearsley (2012: 2) Distance education is defined as planned learning and teaching carried out by the student and the teacher who need special institutional organizations and communication in different places considering the developments in technology and changes in approach. According to İşman (2011: 1), distance education is "an education model carried out thanks to information and communication technologies of educational activities where teachers and students do not have to be in the same places". Kaya (2002: 18) defines distance education as "student counseling, observing and protecting student success and systematically organizing the way of self-employment, each of which is conducted by a team of responsible educators, in showing the material learned".

Distance education, in its simplest terms, can be defined as an educational technology used if the student and the teacher are not in the same environment. Distance education is a form of teaching in which learners are at different times and places from teachers and the interaction between them takes place through printed or electronic communication environments according to another broader definition (Tekinarslan and Güner, 2018: 3).

According to Erturgut (2008: 79), "distance education and open education are often confused concepts. While distance education basically refers to the situation where the student and the teacher are separated as time and place, open education is generally defined as an education system used in higher education and involving pre-organized, voluntary or compulsory learning processes. "

Keegan (1996) defined distance education through the following five features (Güner, 2018: 3): (1) The fact that the teacher and the student are not in separate geographies during the learning process, (2) the effect of an educational institution on the provision of materials and support systems used in education, (3) the use of a technical environment to bring the teacher and the student together, (4) the provision of a communication environment where the student can establish two-way dialogue, (5) the separation of the students from each other from time to time throughout the process for the realization of individual learning.

Societies evolve into a knowledge-intensive way of life in the 21st century, which is the information age, and in this process, education systems that can spread information quickly and accurately are being developed. With the developments in technology, the concept of "Distance Learning" gains great importance at this point. Especially universities and other educational institutions have had the opportunity to reach individuals who live anywhere in the world and are open to learning with the developments in communication technologies. Individuals, wherever they live in the world, have had the opportunity to benefit from these educations without being exposed to discrimination such as religion, language, race, nationality, age and so on at the same time.

A definition that can be made by evaluating the common characteristics of the definitions can be as follows: The system where the teachers and the students can come together on a technological platform and exchange all kinds of information, share, evaluate, test etc. within the framework of the standards required for this education regardless of time and place is called "Distance Learning" system.

The physical space (classroom) where instructors and students will come together is absolutely necessary in the traditional education system. Teachers and students gather at predetermined timeframes and communicate face-to-face in these spaces. Technology is partially utilized while using traditional materials during the course. Exams are also held at the same time and in the same place for everyone as usual. Instructors and students do not need to come together in a physical space at predetermined times and communicate face-to-face throughout the course in the distance education system. Students take these courses at their own request, at their convenience, without any problem in distance. Courses can be online through the internet, or they can also be in the form of accessing enrolled courses via the internet or by e-mail method. Materials such as CDs, DVDs, flash memory and books can also be used as part of this education.

Communications and Technology (Simonson et al., 2014) defines the concept of distance education as "an institution-based education in which the learning group is separated from each other and communication technologies are used to connect students, teachers and resources". According to this definition, distance education has four important features (Gürer, 2018: 4): (1) Distance education is not self-learning, it is institutional based. The teaching process is planned and conducted by an institution; (2) Instructors and learners are separated from each other in terms of space or time or both time and space; (3) It has the characteristics of interaction provided by communication technologies. Communication can be synchronous or asynchronous. Medias such as internet, telephone, e-mail etc. should be integrated into the teaching process as communication technology; (4) A communication network should be established between teachers, students and resources.

It can be said that distance education is an indispensable educational model of the information age we are in and that it will gain greater importance and prevalence with each passing day in the light of definitions and explanations. A large proportion of existing education systems can be expected to become fully distance education in the near future likewise.

III. DISTANCE EDUCATION METHOD

Educational institutions with different structures can be divided into different categories according to the services they provide and can be examined in different dimensions considering these differences. Simonson et al. (2014: 84), addresses distance education in four basic dimensions. The first is that the program has an institutional structure. This is the basic principle that education is separated from self-learning. Students have valid documents such as certificates and diplomas when they finish the education program thanks to this structure. Secondly, the learning and teaching parties act independently of each other in terms of space and time. Thirdly, education programs are provided through communication technologies. Fourthly, students can easily access the necessary educational materials at any time and communicate with teachers. Today, distance education has an organizational structure where learning activity takes place between students and teachers and the appropriate environment and needs are met by managers. Distance education managers should have some

specific skills as well as the general characteristics of classical managers. All activities are provided by a virtual organizational structure in distance education. So that virtual quality should be taken into consideration in the design and management of educational environments. "In this case, distance education should be handled and modeled differently from classical education management" (İşman, 2011: 445).

IV. DISTANCE EDUCATION MODELS

The development of technology has played a major role in the development of the distance education system and continues to play a role. Institutions providing distance education services have become very broad areas by connecting many technological innovations and tools such as satellites, advanced internet infrastructure, personal computers and mobile phones to their education systems.

Since communication was one-way before the Internet started to be used in distance education, developments in this field could be limited. Providing two-way communication with the spread of the Internet has contributed greatly to distance education. Interaction in virtual classes has almost reached the level of interaction in the real classroom environment with the spread of high-speed internet.

The success of the education model to be developed for distance education depends on the fact that it is a model that emphasizes the human factor and that the educational materials are quality and easily accessible. However, models with technical features that maximize the element of interaction are more successful than other distance education models.

İşman (2011: 98) defines distance education models as two groups as "one-way models and two-way models according to the use and interaction status of communication technologies".

The models used in distance education are divided into two main groups depending on the simultaneous and asynchronous (synchronous and asynchronous) communication between teachers and learners (Pılancı, 2018: 80; Işık et al., 2010: 362; Demir, 2014: 205; Midkiff and DaSilva, 2000: 2). However, they are also divided into two depending on the targets and the technological tools used. In non-interactive distance education, communication is one-way; in interactive teaching, it is two-way.

Asynchronous Distance Education Models: Asynchronous distance education is a model that the student aims to learn on its own. There is no simultaneous teacher support in this model; the model provides complete time and space independence to the student. Teachers and learners do not have to communicate simultaneously or to be in the system at the same time (Pılancı, 2018: 82; Akçay and Gökçearsılan, 2016: 1985). The student can access the course content from anywhere at any time. More students can improve themselves by accessing and benefiting from content in this model. The student communicates its requests regarding the content to the instructors via e-mail or forum; it receives the answers to these questions and requests at certain time intervals in the same way.

The transformation of asynchronous distance education into self-learning and the quality of content do not always yield the desired result. Especially due to the fact that the student feels lonely, cannot socialize and similar reasons, users need to work more programmatically in this method. However, it is preferred by many people because students can access the educational environment at any time and place, download documents and send messages to teachers (Hrastinski, 2008: 52).

Asynchronous distance education models are grouped under two headings as one-way passive models and two-way passive models. Students can access pre-prepared course materials and contents at any time in one-way passive models; but there is no mutual communication, they cannot ask questions. This education method represents more of a self-learning approach; students access to relevant content and experience the learning process by themselves with relevant materials without communicating in any way with the instructor (Negash et

al., 2008: 4). One-way radio and television and distance education models can be shown with the letter that is not preferred due to the level of technology today can be example of these models. (İşman, 2011).

In the two-way passive model, a method is followed in which education materials are prepared and stored in advance. The teacher and the student do not meet during the content presentation. Participants benefit from the distance education model by accessing this information at any time and in any number they wish. Information is constantly renewed; questions can be asked between teachers and students and automated reports are produced in this model. Course contents are prepared in an order and stored in a computer environment. A live course or content can be recorded through a camera and stored in a computer media. Students can hear the voice and see the face of teachers in computer environment within this model, but they cannot communicate mutually. There is a one-way communication that the teacher tells and the student listens to. The instructor and student communicate asynchronously through various technologies (Negash et al., 2008: 4-5).

Synchronous Distance Education Models: Teacher can be followed by the students simultaneously while teaching in a simultaneous interactive model. As in the asynchronous education model, teachers and students are geographically independent and may be in different places (Murphy et al., 2011: 584). However, the courses are live and real-time (Demir, 2014: 205; Chen et al., 2004: 2). This education is defined as a virtual classroom system in which teachers and students come together through various systems and methods (Işık et al., 2010: 361). Students can ask questions and get answers to these questions in a certain order. Here, students can be completely disorganized or in groups. On the other hand, in the asynchronous interactive model, students can access the audio and visual course information prepared by the teacher via the internet at any time; they can ask their questions to the teachers with a message. Simultaneous distance education models can be grouped under two headings as "One-Way Passive Models" and "Bi-directional Interactive Models". The courses are conveyed to simultaneous students in one-way passive models; there is no one-to-one communication between the student and the teacher at the time of the lesson. However, the student can access all kinds of materials related to the course at the time of the lesson; it can ask the questions in its mind about the topics it tells in writing by e-mail and so on. The teacher can then answer the questions about the topics it has explained. Both simultaneous courses are held, the necessary safety precautions can be taken and the exams can be held simultaneously; all of these procedures can be recorded. It is a distance education method performed in a live and real-time course environment in bi-directional interactive models (Negash et al., 2008; Falch, 2004). This method, which was previously quite difficult and expensive, has become easier with the development of communication technology and has reached the level of cost that everyone can reach. Since information and questions are communicated at the same time, teachers and users must have smart mobile devices. Students can communicate with teachers from anywhere in a simultaneous interactive model. However, in the asynchronous interactive model, students can access information, videos and similar resources via the internet, ask their questions via e-mail and get their answers by the same method. What needs to be understood when it comes to simultaneous distance education actually is that the same classroom education done traditionally should be moved to a virtual environment and appropriate courses should be taught (Işık et al., 2010: 361). If communication and interaction between groups are high in these virtual classes, success increases to that extent. It can be said that it is quite suitable for students who do not have time problems but have distance problems. Communication paths used in this type of distance education can be defined as systems that transmit sound and image quickly and clearly. Fast internet connection is needed, firstly. Quality of internet infrastructure is the most important element. The most important advantages of this education are that it enables instant feedback, provides more motivation and introduces the obligation to attend to the lesson (Chen et al., 2004: 3).

Mixed Education Models: Mixed or blended education models generally refer to the use of multiple methods together to benefit from the advantages of different education models (Balaman and Tüysüz, 2011). It can be considered as educational models where traditional (face-to-face) education and distance learning technologies are combined (Negash et al., 2008: 4-5) in this context. In the mixed system in distance education, a new method is used by combining simultaneous and asynchronous methods. In mixed distance education,

courses, information, subjects are prepared in advance and stored in a computer environment. This information can be written sources or information prepared by video and other communication methods. In a course with simultaneous communication, the teacher can tell a more efficient lesson by using previously prepared and stored information while in live communication with the students. Students, on the other hand, can interact if they participate in the lesson live, and even if they miss the lesson, they have the opportunity to watch the lesson by entering the record of this course at appropriate times.

As a result, thanks to this method, which has the characteristics of both simultaneous and asynchronous distance education, more options are offered to students. Students can take simultaneous courses and benefit from the advantage of interaction if they wish. If students have a time constraint, they continue their education programs provided that they prefer asynchronous education and watch the course videos produced.

Methodology of The Research

It is aimed to determine how consumers who receive distance education services evaluate distance education in this study. The following hypotheses were formed in order to test the effects of the quality characteristics, perceived benefit and ease and advantages of distance education on consumer satisfaction through the model developed within the scope of the research (Figure 1) in this context:

H1: Quality characteristics of distance education are statistically significant.

H2: The perceived benefit of distance education is statistically significant.

H3: Perceived convenience and advantage in distance education are statistically significant.

H4: Consumer satisfaction from distance English education is high.

H5: Quality characteristics of distance education have a positive effect on perceived benefit.

H6: Quality characteristics of distance education have a positive effect on perceived convenience and advantage.

H7: Perceived benefit from distance education and perceived convenience and advantage have a positive effect on consumer satisfaction.

H8: The effect of quality characteristics of distance education on perceived benefit is H8a according to age groups, H8b according to gender and H8c according to education levels of consumers.

H9: The effect of quality characteristics of distance education on perceived convenience and advantage is different according to age groups of consumers H9a, H9b gender, H9c education levels.

H10: The effect of perceived benefit from distance education on consumer satisfaction is H10a according to age groups, H10b according to gender and H10c according to education levels of consumers.

H11: The effect of perceived convenience and advantage from distance education on consumer satisfaction is H11a according to age groups, H11b according to gender and H11c according to education levels of consumers.

The main mass of the research was determined as the program participants of a business providing distance English education. $N = \frac{p \cdot q}{(Z/e)^2}$ formula was used to calculate the sample size (Yükselen, 2017: 67). In the formula p: the proportion of those who approach distance education positively in the main population; q: 1-p; Z: normal value (+/- 1.96 at 95% security level; e: the amount of error in the estimation of the main mass

ratio refers to +/- 0.05. Data were collected from 403 users by questionnaire method by choosing the convenience sampling method from non-random sampling methods.

The quality characteristics of distance education were utilized from the study of Vinogradova and Kliukas (2015: 1583-1589) and the studies of perceived benefits, conveniences and advantages and satisfaction, Markova, et al. (2017: 685-691) for the scales related to the variables in the conceptual model. In the questionnaire questions, a 5-point Likert scale was used, which determines the level of participation of the respondents in the judgments and is rated as "1-strongly disagree to 5-strongly agree".

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the Research

Analysis Of Research Data And Findings

Demographic Findings

The demographic characteristics of the 403 respondents collected within the scope of the research are given in Table 1. Accordingly, it is seen that the majority of the respondents are 26 years of age and older. Respondents in the 26-35 age group are over 54%. More than half of the respondents appear to be male. When the frequency distributions of educational status are examined, it is possible to say that the respondents have a high level of education profile. As can be seen, 96.28% of the participants have associate degree and higher degree education.

Table 1: Demographic Features of Participants

Gender	n	(%)
Female	191	47,4
Male	212	52,6
Age		
18-25	39	9,7
26-35	218	54,1
36-45	128	31,8
46 and above	18	4,5
Education Status		

Primary education	3	0,74
High school	12	2,98
Associate degree	87	21,59
License	248	61,54
Post Graduate	41	10,17
Doctorate	12	2,98

Reliability Analysis

The reliability of the scales of the variables in the conceptual model was tested with Cronbach's Alpha. The values for the four variables were found to be highly reliable, as can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis Results

Variable	Number of Questions	Cronbach's Alpha
Content Quality	3	0,896
Perceived Benefit	6	0,915
Convenience and Advantage	4	0,898
Customer Satisfaction	2	0,764

Significance Level of Judgments Regarding Model Variables

The significance level of the judgments related to the model variables was analyzed by the Significance Test t-test of the Single Main Mass Arithmetic Mean. According to the results of the analysis in Table 3, the respondents believe in the quality of distance education they have purchased. According to these results, H1 hypothesis was accepted. According to the results in the same table, respondents believe that the benefit they perceive contributes to the convenience and advantage of distance education in the choice of distance English education again. Within the scope of these results, H2 and H3 hypotheses were accepted. The respondents are satisfied with distance education they have purchased (H4 hypothesis is supported) according to the results of the analysis.

Table 3: Significance Levels of Judgments Regarding Model Variables

	Test Value = 3					
	t	Degree of Freeness	Importance level	Mean Range	95% Safety level range	
					Lowest	Highest
General Quality Level	67,01	402	0,000	1,69	1,64	1,74
When learning English over the Internet, the content of the materials used by teachers should be rich.	62,44	402	0,000	1,72	1,66	1,77
When learning English over the Internet, the content of the courses that have been and will be taught should be easily accessed.	59,15	402	0,000	1,69	1,63	1,75
When learning English over the Internet, the methods and content used should be easily understood.	61,39	402	0,000	1,70	1,64	1,75

When learning English over the Internet, it is very important that teachers who provide education communicate professionally and comfortably. (Teacher quality)	61,90	402	0,000	1,70	1,64	1,75
When learning English over the Internet, the applications used should be easily accessible and available. (Accessibility)	60,72	402	0,000	1,69	1,64	1,75
Perceived Benefit	80,42	402	0,000	1,73	1,69	1,78
The English education I get online supports my daily English speaking.	60,73	402	0,000	1,64	1,59	1,70
The English education I get online supports my understanding of the English I use daily.	70,80	402	0,000	1,75	1,70	1,80
The English education I get online supports my writing in English, which I use daily.	65,92	402	0,000	1,73	1,68	1,78
The English education I get online supports my daily English reading.	71,51	402	0,000	1,76	1,72	1,81
The English education I receive online enables me to learn English.	70,80	402	0,000	1,76	1,72	1,81
The English education I get online provides a better career opportunity.	65,91	402	0,000	1,74	1,69	1,79
Convenience and Advantage	66,94	402	0,000	1,68	1,63	1,73
I am learning English over the Internet without interrupting my current work (education).	62,04	402	0,000	1,71	1,66	1,76
The advantage of my online education is that I can learn English wherever there is an internet connection.	59,05	402	0,000	1,70	1,64	1,75
The advantage of my online education is that I can study whenever I want.	56,38	402	0,000	1,66	1,60	1,72
The fee for the education I get online is much cheaper than the education in schools, private teaching institutions and similar places.	58,05	402	0,000	1,70	1,62	1,74
Level of Satisfaction	86,21	402	0,000	1,72	1,73	1,82
Online English education met my expectation.	85,20	402	0,000	1,79	1,75	1,84
I recommend online English education.	77,22	402	0,000	1,74	1,70	1,79

Analysis of the Effect of Distance Education Quality Features on Perceived Benefit and Perceived Ease and Advantage

The effect of distance education quality features on perceived usefulness and perceived convenience and advantage was tested by Simple Regression Analysis. As can be seen in Table 4 showing the analysis results, the regression models established for both variables (perceived usefulness, perceived convenience and advantage) are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Distance education quality characteristics, perceived usefulness of 15.9%, 46.3% and illustrates the perceived ease of advantages (for Perceived Benefits of $R^2 =$

0.159; $R^2 = 0.463$ for perceived convenience and advantage). In line with these results, H_5 and H_6 hypotheses were accepted. Distance education quality characteristics positively affect the perceived benefit and the perceived convenience and advantage.

Table 4: Regression Model Coefficients Related to the Effect of Distance Education Quality Features on Perceived Benefit and Perceived Ease and Advantage

Model		Non-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Importance level	
		B	Standard Error	Beta			
Perceived Benefit	1	Constant	3,081	,191		16,155	,000
		Quality	,352	,040	,399	8,704	,000
	$R=,399$		$R^2=,159$		$F=75,768$		
Perceived Convenience and Advantage	1	Constant	1,394	,178		7,841	,000
		Quality	,700	,038	,680	18,588	,000
	$R=,680$		$R^2=,463$		$F=345,524$		

Analysis of the Perceived Benefit from Distance Education and the Effect of Perceived Convenience and Advantage on Consumer Satisfaction

The effect of perceived usefulness and perceived convenience and advantage on consumer satisfaction was tested by Multiple Regression Analysis. Perceived benefit and perceived convenience and advantage positively affect consumer satisfaction according to the analysis results in Table 5. In the light of this information, H_7 hypothesis was accepted. When the coefficients related to the model are examined, it can be said that while both variables have an effect on satisfaction, the perceived benefit has a slightly higher effect than convenience and advantage.

Table 5: Regression Model Coefficients Related to the Perceived Benefit from Distance Education and the Effect of Perceived Convenience and Advantage on Consumer Satisfaction

Model		Non-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Importance level	Peer Linearity Statistics	
		B	Standard Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	Constant	2,991	,191		14,380	,000		
	Perceived Benefit	,225	,058	,247	3,909	,000	,602	1,755
	Convenience and Advantage	,182	,049	,233	3,697	,000	,504	1,985
$R=,443$		$R^2=,197$		$F=48,939$				

Analysis of the Effect of Distance Education Quality Features on Perceived Benefit, Perceived Ease and Advantage on Demographic Features

Table 6 shows the differences in the effect of distance education quality features on perceived benefit by age, gender and education groups of consumers. The results in the table support H8a and H8c hypotheses and reveal that the effect of distance education quality features on perceived benefit varies according to age groups and education levels of consumers. This relationship is not statistically significant for the 18-25 age group; the effect is higher in the age group of 36 years and older than in the 26-35 age group. In terms of education levels, it is seen that this effect is higher in primary and high school graduates than consumers with other education levels (regression coefficient= 0.640 > 0.299 and 0.324 for primary and high school groups). However, it is seen that the effect of distance education quality features on perceived benefit varies according to the gender of consumers. Therefore, hypothesis H8b was rejected.

Table 6: Results of the Analysis of the Effect of Distance Education Quality Features on Perceived Benefit According to Demographic Features

Demographic features		Model Significance Test		Regression Coefficient	P
		F	p		
Age Groups	18 - 25	3,446	0,071	0,207	0,071
	26 - 35	32,363	0,000	0,319	0,000
	36 and above	43,671	0,000	0,449	0,000
Gender	Male	39,539	0,000	0,354	0,000
	Female	36,040	0,000	0,352	0,000
Education Status	Primary and High School	14,335	0,002	0,640	0,002
	Undergraduate and License	39,605	0,000	0,299	0,000
	Post Graduate	11,634	0,001	0,324	0,001

Table 7 shows the results of the difference analysis of the effect of distance education quality features on perceived convenience and advantage according to the demographic characteristics of consumers. According to the data in the table, the effect in question supports the H 9a , H 9b , H 9c hypotheses, and shows statistical differences according to the age, gender and educational status of the consumers.

Table 7: Results of the Analysis of the Effect of Distance Education Quality Features on Perceived Ease and Advantage According to Demographic Features

Demographic features		Model Significance Test		Regression Coefficient	P
		F	p		
Age Groups	18 - 25	12,727	0,001	0,433	0,001
	26 - 35	162,379	0,000	0,692	0,000
	36 and above	208,511	0,000	0,801	0,000
Gender	Male	151,604	0,000	0,666	0,000
	Female	193,133	0,000	0,735	0,000
Education Status	Primary and High School	25,174	0,000	0,799	0,000
	Undergraduate and License	218,339	0,000	0,664	0,000
	Post Graduate	92,91	0,000	0,831	0,000

Analysis of the Effect of Perceived Benefit from Distance Education on Consumer Satisfaction According to Demographic Features

Table 8 shows the results of the analysis of the effect of perceived benefit from distance education on consumer satisfaction according to the demographic characteristics of consumers. Within the scope of these data, it is seen that the relationship in question varies according to the age, gender and educational status of the consumers. In this context, it can be said that this relationship is stronger in the 18-25 age group compared to other age groups and this effect is higher in women. In terms of education status, it can be stated that the effect of perceived benefit on consumer satisfaction is not statistically significant for users in primary and high school groups ($p > 0.05$), and this effect is higher in graduate users than associate and undergraduate graduates. In the light of this information, H 10a , H 10b and H 10c hypotheses were accepted.

Table 8: Results of the Analysis of the Effect of Perceived Benefit from Distance Education on Consumer Satisfaction According to Demographic Features

Demographic features		Model Significance Test		Regression Coefficient	P
		F	p		
Age Groups	18 - 25	6,937	0,012	0,451	0,012
	26 - 35	51,902	0,000	0,413	0,000
	36 and above	26,422	0,000	0,319	0,000
Gender	Male	29,576	0,000	0,296	0,000
	Female	53,657	0,000	0,459	0,000
Education Status	Primary and High School	0,426	0,525	0,168	0,525
	Undergraduate and License	66,223	0,000	0,374	0,000
	Post Graduate	30,464	0,000	0,657	0,000

Analysis of the Effect of Perceived Convenience and Advantage from Distance Education on Consumer Satisfaction According to Demographic Features

Table 9 shows the results of the analysis of the differences in the effect of perceived convenience and advantage from distance education on consumer satisfaction by age, gender and educational status of consumers. Within the scope of these results, it is seen that the effect in question varies according to the relevant demographic data. Accordingly, it is seen that the effect of perceived convenience and advantage on consumer satisfaction is not statistically significant for the 18-25 age group, and this effect is higher in the age group of 36 years and older in the 26-35 age group and in female participants. When examined in terms of education status, it is seen that the effect of perceived convenience and advantage on consumer satisfaction is not statistically significant in primary and high school groups ($p > 0.5$); and it is higher for participants in master group than associate and undergraduate groups. There was a difference according to gender; this effect was found to be higher in women than men. Accordingly, H1 1a, H1 1b and H1 1c hypotheses were accepted.

Table 9: Results of the Effect of Perceived Convenience and Advantage from Distance Education on Consumer Satisfaction According to Demographic Features

Demographic features		Model Significance Test		Regression Coefficient	P
		F	p		
Age Groups	18 - 25	0,213	0,647	0,071	0,647
	26 - 35	39,078	0,000	0,307	0,000
	36 and above	60,988	0,000	0,395	0,000
Gender	Male	32,733	0,000	0,268	0,000
	Female	49,129	0,000	0,377	0,000
Education Status	Primary and High School	0,087	0,772	0,069	0,772
	Undergraduate and License	53,192	0,000	0,297	0,000
	Post Graduate	90,859	0,000	0,626	0,000

V. CONCLUSION

Education is a very important issue for societies to take their place in the contemporary world and has gained a very different momentum with the change and development in technology in recent years. In the early 90s, while a limited number of individuals could benefit from distance education in the same way as limited technological facilities, today, thanks to the technological infrastructure, the same quality education service has become accessible to everyone at a very low price. Thus, equality of opportunity in education has been ensured and it has become easier for individuals to improve themselves and create career opportunities in the areas they want.

The research carried out within the scope of this study covers the fields of service from an institution providing distance English education and the findings obtained shed light on the marketing strategy to be created when using distance education in English language education. Within the scope of the research, in the light of the studies in the literature, the quality elements of distance education, the perceived benefit of the recipients of the language education in question and the elements of convenience and advantage were evaluated; it was examined to what extent these elements affected the level of satisfaction with the service. The institution providing the service in question has targeted recipients over the age of 18 who request to speak, write, read and understand English easily.

The findings of the research conducted on buyers in this target market reveal the importance of the quality elements of the distance education package. In this context, it is understood from the findings that the content of the materials of the distance education program, easy access to these contents and easy understanding of the content in the same way are important for the recipients. Likewise, the fact that teachers are expert and equipped with strong communication and that the education program can be accessed from anywhere and in any way are important issues that the recipients emphasize. Accordingly, according to the needs and demands of the target market, the enterprises that will provide services in this field should prepare the distance education package, which is the product component, taking these issues into account when creating the marketing mix. In this context, easy access to the program in the internet environment should be ensured to include easily accessible applications, service recipients should be able to easily direct their questions and teachers should provide feedback in the same way, live communication should be made depending on the situation, and the business providing distance education service should focus on the product.

The design of the distance education service must be compatible with the expectations, needs and wishes of the recipient. In this context, perceived usefulness and perceived convenience and advantage elements in the research model should be taken into consideration. The perceived benefit elements that emerge in the analyses where it has a statistically significant level of significance are that the recipient can easily and easily understand English, speak, and gain a good career opportunity. Therefore, the business providing distance

education service needs to offer a product package targeting these benefits, which are considered as self-service. The conveniences and advantages perceived by buyers from distance education in the target market are that they can receive this education without disrupting their own professional activity, access this service from anywhere on the internet and have this service at a more affordable price than formal education. According to these perception elements, the product package and price of distance education are the issues that the business should emphasize in marketing decisions.

Quality characteristics of distance education positively affect the benefit perceived by the recipients and the convenience and advantage. Accordingly, distance education service enterprises that can improve content quality, teacher quality and provide easy accessibility also ensure that buyers are satisfied.

The distribution policy of the distance education service is direct distribution and electronic distribution channel is used. At this point, it is of great importance to access the site from anywhere on the internet and to download the applications easily in accordance with the expectations of the buyers. Therefore, the technical and academic design, which can be easy for buyers to access the site according to the areas where the gravity of the internet is different, will also positively affect the access to the package.

Another of the mixed elements that make up the marketing strategy is the human component, and this element in the distance education service consists of teachers, technical staff and buyers. As the research findings reveal, it is important for the teacher to have expert and communication knowledge and skills in terms of the success of service delivery. As well as teachers, it is of particular importance for the technical team to create the elements that enable buyers to easily access on the website, to ensure that the program is easily accessible and that the applications can be easily downloaded. Performance in this regard will also enable recipients to share their satisfaction and positive feelings and thoughts with their environment. In addition, in recent years, ensuring that buyers participate in important service production is also necessary for distance education service. In this context, getting feedback from the recipients continuously, reviewing the service processes according to the feedback from them will also increase the performance indicators of the service enterprise.

It is important for the buyer who wants to receive distance education service, who needs to be informed and make decisions for this purpose, to know all the main and sub-processes in detail from the beginning. For this reason, the business providing distance education service should make a good analysis of its processes; it should review them with the feedback received from its buyers and arrange them according to the needs.

In the near future, distance education appears to be effective in many areas, including formal education areas. Although the number of enterprises serving in this field is for example small in our country, it should be taken into consideration that competition will increase depending on the increase in the importance of the issue. Therefore, considering and preparing distance education programs suitable for the target recipients as a basic element of various personal development issues, language education and even primary to higher education will provide an advantage to service enterprises in the long term.

In the literature, studies on distance education have been largely carried out by educational scientists, and there are very few studies on marketing. In this context, it is aimed that the research will contribute to the field of educational marketing. The research carried out within the scope of this study covers the receivers and education program of an institution providing English language education. Within the framework of these issues, which should be accepted as an important limitation of the research, if a broader set of programs is made a subject of research, wider information can be accessed and generalization can be made within the scientific framework.

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